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Prediction of Roasted Coffee Bean Quality Based on Sensor Data

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ABSTRACT

The recent increase in global coffee consumption has heightened the importance of producing high-quality coffee. Coffee roasting, a key stage in the processing of coffee beans, significantly impacts the final quality. The quality index of roasted coffee beans can be calculated using data such as temperature, humidity, and other relevant parameters obtained from roasting machines. This information can be used to improve the quality index before the product reaches consumers. In this study, machine learning and deep learning algorithms were employed to predict the quality index of roasted coffee beans using sensor data collected from roasting machines and processed in a laboratory setting. The algorithms used include Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest Regression (RFR), Decision Tree Regression (DTR), XGBoost, and a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) neural network. The performance of each model was evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), R-squared (R^2), Adjusted R-squared, and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) has shown the best performance with 7.9976 MAE, 7.6354 RMSE, 0.9132 Adjusted R^2 , 0.9132 R^2 .

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most popular drinks in the world is coffee that is produced by drying, roasting, grinding, and brewing coffee beans [1], [2], [3]. It is an indispensable drink for social life, business meetings, travel, meals, and other occasions. Many factors affect the aroma and quality of coffee. These factors generally are the size of beans, the density of roasting, the grinding of beans, the preparation of coffee, and the time of brewing [4], [5], [6], [7]. Furthermore, external variables such as coffee density, smell, and roasting parameters also have a significant impact on the overall quality. While the roasting process of coffee beans may at first seem like a simple process of raw coffee beans, the roasting process involves several different factors, including temperature, energy balance, heat

transport and other factors. Depending on each factor, the process has a significant impact on the coffee's quality [8], [9], [10].

The surface properties and Agtron scores play a critical role in determining the roasting process and coffee quality. These parameters provide important information for controlling variables in the roasting process and ensuring the consistency of coffee quality. Therefore, they are crucial for optimizing the roasting process and achieving high quality coffee. In addition, the density of coffee beans has a decisive influence on roasting, flavor and aroma profiles. High density usually indicates high quality and rich flavors. A descriptive summary table based on these characteristics and parameters is shown in Table 1. Currently, processes within the scope of Industry 4.0 can be controlled and optimized by information and communication technologies. Real-time methods are employed to collect, analyze, and discover information about process data. In practice, this information is obtained by analyzing sensor data.

Sensors can generate considerable amounts of data using some form of environmental input. Data is usually collected during a predetermined period. This allows the immediate application of real-time data-based algorithms, control, and interventions to predict the quality of the process [12].

Today, the rapid spread of the transition to smart production systems has increased the importance of quality control management and activities in these production systems. Correct evaluation of process quality is critical important for reducing product quality costs, determining adequacy, and conducting test processes correctly. Additionally, evaluating quality helps companies

Table 1 Characteristics and Color Images of Coffee Beans [11].

Roast Color	Bean Surface	Agtron Number	Common Names	Density (kg/m ³)	Class Number	Look
Light Brown	Dry	80-70	Light, Cinnamon	Density>440	1	
Medium Brown	Dry	70-50	Medium, American	400<Density≤440	2	
Medium Dark	Dry to tiny patches of oil	50-40	Full-city, Espresso	360<Density≤400	3	
Dark Brown	Shiny	40-35	French, Espresso	320<Density≤360	4	
Very Dark Brown	Very shiny	35-30	Italian, Dark French	280<Density≤320	5	
Black Brown	Very shiny	30-25	Dark French	Density<280	6	

anticipate potential weaknesses, improve product design and manufacturing processes, and raise quality standards. [13], [14]. Machine learning and deep learning methods offer the opportunity to effectively use and support quality control processes and management by using data-driven, automated quality analyses in an integrated manner. Process data and quality measurements are correlated, and product quality is predicted based on process data using these predictive machine learning and deep learning techniques. Quality can be estimated with machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines, Random Forest, Regression Methods, and Graphical Models. Quality can also be estimated with deep learning methods such as Computer Vision, Convolutional Neural Networks, and Recurrent Neural Networks guided studies in the field of artificial intelligence in recent years [15], [16], [17].

Coffee quality is strongly correlated with the chemical composition of roasted beans affected by the combination of green beans and post-harvest processing conditions such as drying, storage, roasting, and grinding [18]. The distinguishing characteristics of coffee such as flavor and aroma develop during the roasting process in which the coffee beans were exposed to a series of reactions that changed their chemical composition [19]. During the roasting process, in addition to moisture loss and chemical reactions, significant changes occur in terms of color, volume, mass, pH and density [20]. An exothermic reaction involving proteins, chlorogenic acid and trigonelline are compounds that affect the color, flavor, and aroma of roasted coffee beans [21]. It discussed the genetic and non-genetic factors influencing the type and variance of coffee quality and provided samples of various quality levels [22]. The random forest method is used for the Arabica coffee bean type in a data set acquired from an outside source to predict coffee quality and investigate the factors that influence coffee quality [23]. A deep learning-driven quality assessment system is proposed for estimating the degree of roasting of coffee beans. The different machine-learning algorithms proposed for the prediction of cup coffee quality based on a series of measurements made on roasted coffee beans [24], [25].

In this study, data collected every minute from sensors placed in the chambers in the roasting machine and capable of reading temperature data during the roasting process of coffee beans were used to estimate coffee quality. At the end of the one-hour roasting process, the density quality of the roasted coffee beans was determined in the laboratory and matched with 60 sensor data collected in one hour. Then, the density quality of the coffee bean was estimated using machine learning and deep learning algorithms and analyzed by comparing model performances.

2 METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 presents an understandable framework for predicting coffee quality with a procedure stage-by-stage. According to the diagram in Figure 1, the data set is split into a k number of folds. Each fold is then used once as a test set while the $k - 1$ the other folds form the training set. This process is repeated for k fold. For each fold, the performance of the model is evaluated, and a performance metric is calculated. The performance metrics calculated for each fold are averaged. This is conducted to enhance the assessment of the model's overall performance. The average performance metrics and other statistical measures are used to evaluate the success level of the model.

Figure 1: The methodology for predicting coffee quality.

2.1 Dataset

In this study, it is used the “Production Quality Dataset” obtained from Kaggle Datasets [26]. The Coffee Roasting Machine is equipped with five chambers (Ch#), each featuring three temperature sensors (TS#). Additionally, the machine is equipped with a humidity sensor (HS) and a layer height sensor (LHS). The placement of three sensors at various locations within the chamber is designed to guarantee precise temperature control in each section, ensuring uniform roasting of the material. Figure 2 represents the coffee roasting process diagram. The processing of raw materials through the kiln occurs within a one-hour timeframe. During this period, data is received from temperature, humidity, and level height sensors every minute. At the end of this hour, a sample of the roasted coffee beans is taken, and its quality (density) is measured in the laboratory. Input and output data are stored in separate tables. The input data table includes date, hour, minute, temperature data reading from sensors every minute, the height of the raw material layer, and its moisture content. The output

Figure 2: Coffee roasting process diagram [26].

Table 2 Dataset Descriptive Statistics Information

Variable	Count	Mean	Std	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max
T_data_1_1	25301	250.19	27.72	161.91	228.90	250.00	271.33	350.61
T_data_1_2	25301	249.98	27.62	150.08	228.80	249.86	271.16	349.93
T_data_1_3	25301	250.19	27.60	150.03	229.00	250.00	271.36	350.48
T_data_2_1	25301	350.59	29.89	249.88	329.15	350.33	371.80	499.81
T_data_2_2	25301	350.95	28.99	280.11	329.31	350.00	372.06	499.68
T_data_2_3	25301	350.23	28.90	250.16	329.36	350.16	371.50	449.26
T_data_3_1	25301	500.75	50.72	300.00	464.56	502.03	536.90	649.86
T_data_3_2	25301	501.91	51.10	370.41	464.53	502.30	537.13	749.81
T_data_3_3	25301	502.43	51.06	370.33	465.51	502.60	538.16	749.58
T_data_4_1	25301	348.80	29.95	220.58	327.30	348.88	370.58	450.96
T_data_4_2	25301	349.55	29.77	250.16	327.83	349.08	370.75	480.56
T_data_4_3	25301	349.71	30.88	200.85	328.08	349.48	371.13	499.63
T_data_5_1	25301	249.69	27.20	150.73	228.90	249.55	270.23	349.95
T_data_5_2	25301	249.93	27.21	150.4	229.03	249.95	270.86	347.58
T_data_5_3	25301	249.71	27.26	151.20	228.86	249.81	270.46	349.75
H_data	25301	174.69	13.76	149.47	163.20	174.36	186.16	200.66
AH_data	25301	7.49	1.14	3.15	6.73	7.50	8.26	11.62
Quality	25301	402.69	46.10	228.00	372.00	408.00	439.00	505.00

data table includes the date, time, and coffee bean density, serving as an indicator of quality, which is analyzed in the laboratory on an hourly basis.

Descriptive statistics, encompassing measures of central tendency, variability, and distribution, serve as a foundational framework for researchers and analysts to extract meaningful insights from complex datasets. The importance of these statistical measures is elucidated through their contribution to data summarization, exploration, and subsequent inference. Furthermore, descriptive statistics serve as a fundamental tool for exploring underlying patterns, trends, and relationships within a dataset. Descriptive statistics for the data set are given in Table 2.

2.2 Data Pre-Processing

Input and output data are merged into a singular database using a SQL statement utilizing date and time primary characteristics. In an hour, a quality value is calculated from 60 input data points. The particular output is generated for 60 input data points. An outlier analysis is conducted to find anomalies or abnormal observations in the dataset. This study eliminates misleading or inadequate observations that could affect the results. Finally, the input data obtained every minute during the period of an hour is averaged and compared with the quality value obtained at the ending of the hour. This operation eliminates duplicate observations that give equal results, without any reduction in dimension. In data splitting, the split ratios of test and training data are important. In the studies conducted in the literature, researchers generally recommend a 70/30 or 80/20 split of the training/test set. However, the ratio may vary depending on the size of the data set or the characteristics of the study. It has been observed that increasing the ratio of the training data set can increase or decrease the performance of the model [27]. For this reason, the 80/20 training/test set ratio recommended by the researchers was preferred in our study.

Table 3 Performance Comparison of The Algorithms.

Algorithm	MAE	RMSE	Adjusted R ²	R ²
Support Vector Regression	11.7431	16.12481	0.8536	0.8551
Decision Tree Regression	0.2412	0.3165	0.8989	0.8996
Random Forest Regression	14.8097	19.5600	0.8166	0.8132
XGBoost	11.1621	14.6541	0.9022	0.9022
Multi-Layer Perceptron	7.9976	7.6354	0.9132	0.9132

3 RESULTS AND DICSUSSION

In this section, the performance criteria of the algorithms used in the study are compared and analyzed by changing their parameters. It is found that changing the model parameters has a significant effect on the model performance. The results of prediction obtained by different regression algorithms (SVR, Random Forest, Decision Tree, XGBoost, and Multilayer Perceptron) were compared in this study. Each model experienced 10-fold cross-validation, and the hyperparameters were optimized using the grid search technique. The SVR model performed more effectively when the parameters C, epsilon, and gamma changed to C = 2, epsilon = 0.02, and gamma = 0.1. The number of trees in the Random Forest algorithm increased from 100 to 500, with 500 resulting in the best result. The maximum depth in the Decision Trees algorithm has been changed from 1 to 20, and it was found that a depth range of 10-15 was suitable to avoid overfitting. The optimum result of the XGBoost algorithm was obtained with 150 trees, a maximum depth of 7, and a learning rate of 0.05. The Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) algorithm has changed the number of neurons and layers. Six layers and twelve neurons generated the best results. The optimal parameters and performance metrics of each model are shown in Table 3.

While analyzing the performance metrics in Table 3, the MLP model showed the lowest MAE and RMSE, alongside the highest Adjusted R² and R² values. The XGBoost algorithm shows lower error rates and exhibits strong ability to explain and accuracy for prediction. Although decision tree regression shows low error rates, it could show overfitting for overall performance. whereas, random forest and support vector regression showed less effective compared to other models. The MLP model has shown significant performance in accurately predicting the roasted quality index and obtaining the most accurate results.

4 CONCLUSION

This study examines predicting of roasted coffee bean quality using sensor data collected through the roasting process. Various regression-based approaches, including support vector regression, decision tree regression, random forest regression, XGBoost, and multilayer perceptron, were applied using cross-validation and performance metrics such as MAE, RMSE, Adjusted R², and R², with a comparative analysis of the results performed. The results indicate that the MLP model was superior performance. These findings show that data-driven methodologies are effective in modelling coffee bean roasting processes and emphasize the possibility of intelligent systems that include sensors and comparable tools for enhancing quality control in coffee production.

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